

HEAVY KARMIC DEBTS: TIBETAN MENSTRUATION EXPERIENCES, PERCEPTIONS, AND ATTITUDES¹

Rdo rje dpal 'byor རྡོ་རྗེ་དཔལ་འབྱུང་། (Duoji huanjiao 多吉环角)

ABSTRACT

This paper explores historical beliefs and practices surrounding menarche and menstruation, focusing on the experiences of five Tibetan women born between 1960 and 1972 who grew up in a traditional society where period products were not initially available and only gradually became so in the late 1990s. These women adhered to the cultural norm of silence regarding menstruation. Discussions about the experience were considered disgraceful. They internalized their menarche-related fear, confusion, and anxiety. Furthermore, dealing with menstrual blood posed challenges, leading to embarrassment and humiliation. Menstruation grew interwoven with taboos and restrictions as society changed, including abstention from sex, certain foods, and drinks, and refraining from visiting religious sites and the family's shrine room. Insights are provided on the cultural perceptions and practices surrounding menstruation in Tibetan society, shedding light on the evolving dynamics of this aspect of women's lives.

KEYWORDS

Bon skor (Wangshenke), menarche, menstruation, menstrual products, shame, Tibetan women

INTRODUCTION

Menarche is defined as the first menstrual period in a female adolescent and typically happens between the ages of ten and sixteen, with the average age of onset being 12.4 years. The onset of menarche is determined by socioeconomic conditions, genetics, general health, nutritional status, and family size.² Yet, beyond the biological significance, menarche holds profound cultural weight within Tibetan society, shaping notions of femininity and womanhood across generations.

Menstruation, commonly known as periods, is the natural process in which the uterus sheds its lining, including blood, mucus, and cellular debris, through the vagina, typically lasting for three to seven days. The menstrual cycle prepares the female body for the possibility of pregnancy. When pregnancy doesn't occur, hormones instruct the uterus to release its lining, leading to periods. The cycle repeats after a period begins.³

In the remote rural areas of northwestern China, Tibetan women carry with them untold stories and intimate experiences of menstruation, a narrative often shrouded in silence.

¹ I sincerely thank the multiple reviewers and editors, who helped make this paper better.

² See Lacroix, et al. (2023).

³ Better Health Channel (2024). <https://www.betterhealth.vic.gov.au/health/conditionsandtreatments/menstrual-cycle>, accessed 20 October 2023.

This paper ventures into this realm, delving into the menstrual journeys of five Tibetan women. Through their individual accounts, we embark on a journey through time, exploring the evolution of attitudes and practices surrounding menstruation within their intricate cultural and socioeconomic contexts.

These five women, born and raised locally, offer more than personal stories, they serve as torchbearers for their female predecessors, amplifying the voices and predicaments regarding menstruation of generations past. Growing up herding livestock (sheep, goats, cows) and cultivating crops of wheat, barley, and canola, they were immersed in the rhythm of rural life, where access to formal education was a distant dream and literacy remained out of reach.

Within these narratives lie echoes of resilience and adaptation, as women navigate the ebb and flow of menstruation amidst changing tides of modernity. From the scarcity of period products to the gradual embrace of female hygiene products in the late twentieth century, their stories mirror the broader societal shifts occurring within Tibetan communities.

In the pages that follow, we share personal stories, cultural views, and historical background to highlight the different menstrual experiences of women in Tibetan culture. By seeing through their eyes, we can better understand the importance of menstruation in the past, present, and future, celebrating the quiet rhythms that are a key part of womanhood.

METHODOLOGY AND ETHICS

This study centers on Tibetan women residing in rural Bon skor (Wangshenke) Community, Bya mdo (Shagou) Township, Mang ra (Guinan) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. From February to July of 2023, using semi-structured interviews, five local women born between 1960 and 1972 were interviewed about their menstrual experiences.

These women were chosen because they were willing to share their experiences of menstruation and their first-hand experience of living in a time when there was a shortage of menstrual products.

Not all women were prepared to speak openly on this topic. For example, a woman (b. 1948) whom I consulted laughed uncomfortably and was unwilling to speak openly about her menstrual experience, declaring there was nothing special about it, and that it was shameful to discuss such a private matter. She emphasized women who discussed menstruation in public were once believed to have mental problems. She was unsure if young people talking more openly about menstruation was a good thing.

The interviews were conducted on a voluntary basis, with participants making informed decisions about their involvement. Before the interviews, each participant was directly approached and asked if they wished to be interviewed and if they consented to include their original voices in the paper. All participants agreed, and this consent was audio-recorded as an additional measure.

Throughout the interview process, great care was taken to ensure that no pressure was exerted on the participants. The interviews were conducted in a respectful and non-coercive manner.

Due to the participants' illiteracy, written consent forms were not feasible. However, verbal consent was obtained and recorded. Participants were assured that their real names would not be disclosed to protect their sensitive information and personal privacy. Instead, only their years of birth were provided to maintain anonymity and shield them from potential stigma.

Furthermore, participants were informed that the audio-recordings would be securely stored on the author's phone, protected by security passwords. They were assured that access to these recordings would be restricted to the author alone.

As a member of the community, there was a preexisting level of trust established between the author and the participants, further ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of the interview process.

Each woman was interviewed using a set of questions and encouraged to express themselves freely. Each interview took forty to fifty minutes and was conducted entirely in Amdo Tibetan dialect. All the conversations were audio-recorded on a cellphone and later translated and analyzed in English by the author. After transcribing each interviewee's account from the audio-recording, some repetitive information was omitted, but the essence of their accounts was captured. Furthermore, their words were organized based on relevance rather than the sequence of the questions.

Additionally, I drew some conclusions based on my personal experience in the discussion section. Born and raised in the local community, I have developed a long-term relationship with residents and gained rich insights into their lifestyle, social structure, and changes. My education in local boarding schools, from primary to high school, allowed me to interact with Tibetan students from both herding and farming backgrounds. I witnessed challenges schoolgirls face regarding reproductive health, menarche, and menstruation. Importantly, I understand the landscape of girls' reproductive health education in local schools and teachers' attitudes. Consequently, I feel I have the credibility to draw conclusions alongside the experiences of these five female consultants.

LITERATURE REVIEW⁴

Literature about Tibetan women's menstrual experiences is limited. A search for 'Tibetan menstruation' on google scholar returned 13,600 results on June 10, 2024. Overall findings fall in three categories: perceptions about menstruation, traditional medical treatment for menstrual ailments, and the onset age for menarche among girls.

The early Tibetan physician, G.yu thog yon tan mgon po (2006 [1982]:371), attributed the existence of womanhood to *bsod nams dman pa* 'low merit'. He regarded *zla mtshan* 'menstruation', *nu ma* 'breasts', and the *mngal* 'uterus' as special characteristics of the female anatomy. He also attributed a number of women's ailments to *skye ba dman* 'inferior birth' of the female body.

Relatedly, McGranahan (2010) points out that menstrual blood, as well as blood from childbirth or miscarriage, are deemed especially impure, e.g., menstruating women are prohibited from entering sacred locales. Spafford (2015) similarly notes the reluctance of Tibetan women to enter religious sites during their menstrual cycle in fear of religious transgression. Interviews from research on the current paper reflect these findings, with Lha mtsho and 'Brug skyid stating that menstruation is polluting. Although not perceiving themselves as inferior to men due to menstruation, they acknowledge their reduced social position in comparison to their male counterparts.

⁴ Keywords including *menstruation*, *menarche*, and *Tibetan women* were used to search literature in English, Tibetan, and Chinese on <https://scholar.google.com>, <https://xueshu.baidu.com>, <https://www.cnki.net>, <https://library.bdrc.io>, <https://www.nstl.gov.cn>, and <https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/tchs20>.

Tibetan medical literature underscores the significance of menstruation with Jiao et al.'s (2022) comparative study of herbal remedies used for menstrual disorders in various regions. Their research reveals that Tibetan women commonly use the entire *Cirsium soubiei* (Franch.) Mattf. plant⁵ for heavy or prolonged bleeding (menorrhagia) and the aerial portion of *Lagotis breviflora* Maxim⁶ for menstrual regularity. Li et al.'s (2018) study of herbal remedies identified the application of *Carthamus tinctorius*,⁷ a common herbal remedy in Tibetan regions, for addressing dysmenorrhea and amenorrhea in local clinics. Bright (2012) explored more broadly the convergence of biomedicine, cultural notions, and religious perceptions of women and gender in modern Tibetan medical texts regarding menstruation.

Several studies sought to pinpoint the typical age at which Tibetan girls experience menarche. Dpal bzang rgyal mtsho (2010) found girls typically commence menstruation between the ages of twelve to fifteen, often preceded by symptoms such as physical frailty, fatigue, back and abdominal pain, and breast swelling. Precautions during this phase are also presented. Zhang et al. (1984) reported the average age to be 16.84 and drew parallels with the menstrual patterns of women across multiple ethnic groups in China. Xiao et al. (2008) presented variances in the onset of menarche between urban and rural Tibetan girls, citing the age of menarche in Lha sa (Lasa) as 13.63, whereas the rural average of Nag chu (Naqu) was 13.70. Additionally, they identified seasonal surges in menarche during summer and autumn.

According to Meng et al. (2014:7), the average age of menarche among tertiary education female students in the Tibetan Autonomous Region (TAR, Xizang) was 13.5, with a dysmenorrhea occurrence rate of 71.5%, underscoring the lack of accessible menstrual education. Furthermore, Zouqiang (1996) associated the earlier onset of menarche in Lha sa with the regional economy, cultural influences, living standards, nutritional intake, and overall health conditions.

In summary, the modest literature reviewed has broadly addressed perceptions around the menstrual cycle among Tibetan women and traditional herbal remedies for menstrual disorders. A few studies have delved into the onset of menarche and variances in age onset due to young women's geographic, economic, and nutritional status. One author encapsulates the convergence of biomedicine, cultural notions, and religious perceptions about menstruation in the modern Tibetan medical textbook.

INTERVIEWS

Lha mtsho (b. 1960, 63 years old)

I was fifteen and weeding in the field. I observed blood when I urinated near the field and panicked, convinced that something was very wrong with me. Worried and terrified, I hurried home to see my mother. I couldn't help sobbing as I described the incident. She said it was normal for girls and tried to calm me. I couldn't believe this and rolled frantically on the ground. I frequently urinated to check whether there was blood. It drove me crazy when there was blood. I was agitated and

⁵ A stemless, perennial herb growing on forest margins, roadsides, fallow fields, flooded lands, fields, and moist places by water at 1,900-4,800 m in Kan su'u (Gansu), Ningxia, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai), Zi khron (Sichuan), and Dbus gtsang (Xizang) http://www.efloras.org/florataxon.aspx?flora_id=2&taxon_id=200023695, accessed 10 September 2023.

⁶ The native range of this species is eastern Qinghai to southwest Gansu. This perennial grows in subalpine and subarctic biomes <https://powo.science.kew.org/taxon/urn:lsid:ipni.org:names:813199-1>, accessed 10 September 2023.

⁷ *Gur kum* (Tibetan name), Honghua (Chinese name), safflower, a commonly used herbal medicine.

couldn't sleep at night when I was menstruating. I couldn't accept it until I was older, and even then, psychological acceptance took a long time.

Before my menarche, I had noticed menstrual blood inside women's robes and on their legs, but I didn't expect the same would happen to me. Slowly, I realized that all women had this experience and encountered difficulties dealing with menstrual blood because of a lack of menstrual hygiene products.

No one told me that I would menstruate before my first period. My mother was the only one I talked with about my menarche. Telling others about my periods would have been humiliating since no one discussed this publicly. I tried not to reveal that I was menstruating during my periods.

I didn't know that women go through menstruation until I became an adult and gave birth. No one told me this before.

It's distressing and pitiful to recall local women's experience with menstruation without sanitary pads or underwear, especially compared to women today. It was common for women to spot the felt on the adobe stove, their trousers, and robes. Letting menstrual blood flow into a pair of trousers was the best option. Nevertheless, we didn't think we were unlucky or poor. Instead, we thought we were beautiful, living a good life, and satisfied. Women nowadays are lucky to have access to various disposable sanitary napkins and underwear that can be changed daily. We didn't dream of such things in our time.

During communal work or gatherings, a menstruating woman often asked for assistance from other women to see if her trousers were spotted with menstrual blood to avoid embarrassment. We didn't care much when the people around us were all females. Young women were shyer and more careful than older women.

There were cases in which local men enjoyed discussing women's menstrual discharge on their beds. Also, discussing this was not exceptional among women.

Once, when I was on my way home from fetching water, a car passed me, throwing out packs of menstrual paper. I had never seen this before and didn't know what it was used for. Thinking it was good for wrapping medicines, I gave it to a local Tibetan doctor, who was pleased. Later, when I was around twenty, I realized that paper was for menstruation.

Later, we had access to long and wide menstrual papers. Unlike modern sanitary pads, which can be used directly, we needed to fold them into a pad. They were better than cloth, but the problem was we didn't have underwear, hindering the effective use of menstrual pads. For example, many times, we were ridiculed when menstrual pads fell to the ground through our loose trousers.

We had trousers, but my older generations didn't. They wore Tibetan robes daily. Elders would say young women are lucky because we have trousers, so our robes won't be stained.

Previously, local women did not refer to menstruation as *zla mtshan/grang gzhi*, which is what we call it now. Instead, we called it *gos rdzod* 'something that spoils fabric'.

Some say menstrual discharge can't be shown to the sky, so I buried the sanitary pads under ash.

Women used to blame menstruation for staining their beautiful Tibetan robes, especially when participating in wedding ceremonies. We often complained about having to menstruate and admired men whose lives were free from this.

We didn't understand menstruation correctly. I thought menstruation was shameful and should be hidden. But I don't think that way now because it's nothing bad like stealing or harming others. It is a natural experience for women. Perhaps today's tendency to discuss menstruation openly has influenced me. Young generations are now educated and understand what is shameful. Doctors are also educating women about menstruation.

To some extent, local women have been publicly discussing menstruation among themselves. For example, if we were outside and a woman had her period, she would ask for a sanitary pad from other women without hesitation. This was unthinkable years ago.

Because of my traumatic menarche experience, teaching girls about menstruation at school would be good. Otherwise, they might suffer mental turmoil.

I told my daughter about menstruation, telling her not to be scared. Once, she came from school and asked for a cup of tea with brown sugar. I was puzzled and asked why. She said, "Girls drink brown tea with brown sugar at school when menstruating. They said it could stop the menstrual blood."

Girls had periods for a few days and then stopped, so they thought it was because of the brown sugar tea.

When I was in my early thirties, some women said that there was underwear that could help prevent your menstrual paper from falling. That was true. Later, we could purchase these from our local township town, which made things much more convenient. We had to wear one pair of briefs for a long time because, unlike today, we didn't have others to change into.

One time, some local women went for a free physical check at the township center, and a doctor told us to wear underwear and wash and dry it in the sun. We were also told the importance of changing underwear frequently for hygiene. This was unrealistic for us, and we criticized the doctor's advice on our way back: "Ridiculous! How is it possible to change underwear regularly? Who has that many pairs of underwear?"

Everyone agreed, and some said, "What if others see us washing our underwear?"

We only talked about menstruation with women we were close to. If a woman had severe abdominal pain during menstruation, she wouldn't admit it, even if a doctor asked. The same was true for me. Everything related to menstruation was hidden.

We did all the usual chores during our periods. For example, when irrigating fields, our feet might have been immersed in cold water all night or all day. We didn't know that it impacted our health until later when hospitals were easily accessible.

I heard women say a pregnant woman will not menstruate. Besides, they often say that when a woman resumes her period a few months after childbirth, there is the possibility of becoming pregnant, and if she doesn't menstruate for a year or so, she won't become pregnant during that time.

In the past, locals believed there was a connection between menarche and sexuality. It was thought girls began menstruating when they had sex with men. When a young girl menstruates, locals tend to gossip she must have had sex at a young age. People also would talk about girls' sexuality based on the size of their breasts. If a girl has bigger breasts, they believe she is sexually active.

There are no regulations on women practicing religious rituals during their periods. Nevertheless, some local women resist going to religious assembly halls or practicing religious rituals such as fasting during menstruation. Menses have a bad polluting odor, so avoiding approaching sacred places during menstrual periods is good.

It is obvious that women have lower social positions than men, but menstruation is not what makes us inferior.

Mkha' 'gro skyid (b. 1963, 60 years old)

It was common for local women to have premarital sex.

I had my menarche around fifteen but told no one, not even my mother and sisters. Before my menarche, my mother told me to be careful and emphasized that having sex would lead to menstruation.

We wore Tibetan robes. We had no trousers or menstrual pads, so menses stained our robes. Those products might have been available elsewhere, but we were in remote areas and couldn't go to places with a market. My first visit to the local township center was when I was around thirty.

During our periods, we did usual work, including fetching water, collecting firewood and cow dung, driving livestock to water, crossing rivers barefoot, working in fields, etc. Consequently, my female contemporaries now have health problems such as backaches and joint pains. All these issues were caused by overwork in the past, especially during our periods.

I was worried during my menarche. I hid everything about it from others. I thought I should be ashamed of it since no one discussed it publicly.

Once, I had an irregular period and was too ashamed to tell anyone, including a male Tibetan doctor. I was too embarrassed to talk about my symptoms and the amount of my menses unless the doctor asked me about it. He mostly took my pulse and prescribed Tibetan medicine. Once I had an IV for an irregular menstrual discharge.

As I grew older, I gradually consulted a close sister about my menstrual problem but no one else.

When I was a child, I saw my mother's and other women's robes with inside stains of menstrual blood. I initially felt curious and scared, but later, I became accustomed to it. My mother often told me not to carelessly place her robe inside out where others might see it.

Women never talked about menstruation publicly. Locals thought a person who did this was mentally ill. Young generations talk about menstruation publicly today. I think it's fine if they don't discuss it in the presence of male relatives. Children now go to official schools and don't know what they shouldn't talk about. Thus, there are cases when young girls speak about menstruation in the presence of their fathers, which is mortifying.

When you compare our menstrual experience with that of contemporary women, we experienced much more difficulty dealing with it, but we didn't think it was hard at that time. It seemed normal.

Unlike my mother, I talked about menstruation with my daughter. I told her not to be afraid and worried when having her menarche. Girls must be educated about menstruation before it begins. Otherwise, they may have many emotional and mental challenges.

We should take menstruation seriously since it can signal serious health issues. For example, one of my female relatives had a lot of bleeding, considered it shameful, and hid it. Finally, when it worsened, family members became aware of this and took her to the hospital, but it was too late, and she died.

Rta mgrin (b. 1968, 55 years old.)

My menarche at fifteen was an unhappy, ill-fated experience. I didn't know about menstruation and that all women menstruate. I had no knowledge of the differences in the reproductive systems of men and women nor of the relationship between menstruation and pregnancy for a long time after I experienced menarche. I had never heard anyone discuss it, and I had never been told about it. As a result, I was scared and shocked when I menstruated the first time.

Our female predecessors wore Tibetan robes and used no period products. Conversely, we wore trousers and used pieces of cloth to deal with menstrual blood. Since there was no underwear, the typical practice was to use a strip of cloth as a waistband and fasten a cloth pad to it. Fabric was relatively scarce, so we used a piece of cloth for a day. I was often anxious that I would be humiliated by others seeing my menstrual blood.

Zla mtshan and *sked pa* are common terms for menstruation. *Zla mtshan* is disturbing and troubling, but it's also good because doctors say unclean things are discharged from the uterus.

Locals used to say that menstrual blood-stained cloth shouldn't be thrown anywhere because it would offend *klu*,⁸ so we were careful. Used menstrual material was often buried deep underground or in ash. Locals tend to say that being born as a man is *bsod nams che* 'great merit' while born as a woman is of *bsod nams chung* 'less merit' and heavy *lan chags* 'karmic debts from past action'. Women had to experience menstruation, pregnancy, and childbirth because of these 'karmic debts'. As I grew older, I admired men's lives and understood the difference between men and women.

Locals used to say sexual experience determined the onset of menstruation, which was untrue. Because of that idea, locals were generally surprised to learn a teenage girl menstruated early, gossiped about her sexual experiences, and generally denigrated her. This might be why girls kept their menarche secret, viewing it as shameful and wanting to prevent unnecessary criticism and denigration from parents.

Now, everything has changed. Girls and women don't consider menstruation as shameful as they did in the past. Mothers tell their daughters what they know about menstruation. It's no longer a secret. It's increasingly an open topic among women but not among men, especially not with male relatives.

Similarly, I no longer consider menstruation shameful. We should not keep it as a secret because it is natural for all women. We did nothing wrong to cause menstruation. Girls previously suffered from fear and shyness because of menstruation. This situation is better now. Teenage girls receive information at school about menstruation and physical reproduction. Doctors also offer advice to local women on health care, which is extremely good.

In terms of restrictions during the menstrual period, sex is believed to be inappropriate as it might cause gynecological diseases. In addition, cold water and heavy physical labor are detrimental to our health during this time. However, these beliefs did not exist in the past, and I didn't care. My finger joints are all swollen now because I frequently encountered cold water.

In my late twenties, packets of sanitary towels costing 0.5 RMB became locally available. However, underwear wasn't available until some years after the arrival of towels. We needed underwear to use the sanitary paper effectively. Because of financial difficulty, we used a packet of sanitary papers for a long time and couldn't change the pads as frequently as women do now. There are now many choices for sanitary pads. For example, ones with an adhesive back to keep the pad in place and cotton surfaces, which girls prefer. However, most older women prefer traditional sanitary paper they fold into pads. They think modern pads have too much plastic and are bad for their health.

I used to see women wearing two to three pairs of trousers together during their periods. I couldn't do that because I only had one pair of trousers. Trousers were rarely washed because of

⁸ *Klu* 'naga' are serpent spirits classified as one of the eight classes of gods and demons, or as animals or demi-gods. They live beneath the earth's surface or in water, trees, or rocks, and are believed to have magical powers and wealth. They are responsible for certain illnesses transmitted to humans (<https://www.rigpawiki.org/index.php?title=Naga>, 10 September 2023).

limited tap water. Instead, trousers were dried in the sunshine, beaten with sticks, or kneaded with the hands to clean them. All trousers were black and dark blue then, which concealed menstrual blood.

An unpleasant situation faced today is that some women don't care where they discard their used sanitary pads. Recently, when community members collectively picked up garbage to clean the environment, we found sanitary towels everywhere, which was disgusting. All the women strongly criticized those who were so careless. In the past, women had to be careful with their menstrual blood, but now they are too careless, which is not good.

I didn't have any pain during my periods. One problem I had was that after having a contraceptive ring fitted at the hospital, the doctor told me to rest and avoid heavy labor for some time. I ignored this and carried a heavy bag on my back, which caused discomfort in my abdomen and profuse bleeding. I returned to the hospital, and the doctor solved my problem by prescribing medicine.

Women hid everything, including menorrhagia, which was thick, whitish, and yellowish or greenish vaginal discharge (leucorrhoea) in the past. This resulted in death in some cases. Teenage girls were shy and too embarrassed to discuss menstruation, while older women didn't care much and chatted about it openly among their intimate friends.

Lha skyid rgyal (b. 1970, 53 years old)

No one told me about menstruation when I was a young girl. As a result, I felt overwhelmed and scared when I experienced my menarche at thirteen. I wore pants and used a piece of cloth as a menstrual pad.

At that time, locals said a girl wouldn't menstruate unless she had had sex with men. That wasn't true for me, but I hid everything about menstruation from others for fear others might humiliate me about the onset of menstruation at an early age.

I used a piece of cloth many times. It was difficult for a young girl. We fastened the cloth menstrual pad to a cloth strip we used as a belt. There was no underwear. Later, we could buy sanitary pads in the local township town.

Nobody discussed menstruation publicly, but I noticed older women's menstrual discharge inside their robes.

I often think women's life is tough because of menstruation and childbirth. I wish to be a male in my next life.

I now feel pity about my menstrual experience, which caused a lot of mental stress and physical discomfort.

People used to regard the menstrual period as shameful, but now young people talk about it openly without shame or hesitation. Some traditional women remain careful about discussing it and are uncomfortable with open discussion. I also think it's not good to talk about menstruation excessively in daily life. We must choose the appropriate time and occasion to talk about it. The topic of menstruation is something we should still be modest about in certain situations, for example, in the presence of men and especially male relatives. We should not reveal issues about our menstrual discharge to others.

There were many embarrassing moments before we had menstrual products. Women accidentally exposed their menses on their robes or pants. In that case, we would often inform the woman so that she could take care of it; otherwise, men would humiliate her.

I strongly advocate schools educating girls about menstruation because it's good for their physical and mental health.

We didn't have specialized doctors, and women didn't have as many health problems as they seem to have now. Or maybe women in the past hid their physical discomfort.

A few years ago, I consulted a doctor in a Tibetan hospital about having abdominal pain and irregular bleeding during my period. I stayed there for a week until I recovered.

Women used to hide menstrual issues, which led to severe, even deadly gynecological diseases. It's important to tell doctors your issues and not be shy.

Some local individuals believe menstrual blood is impure and may emit an unpleasant odor, potentially contaminating religious images or the shrine room during the period. I heard menstrual blood during menarche was considered precious and had applications in medicine. I'm curious if there is any truth to this.

Some women choose not to visit religious sites, including their family's shrine room, during menstruation due to a belief that it is impure. I hadn't encountered this perspective before, but it does make me hesitate to visit religious sites during my periods.

'Brug skyid (b. 1972, 51 years old)

I first menstruated at thirteen. I was scared and anxious but gradually calmed and accepted it since I had seen older women's menstrual blood inside their robes. I didn't tell anyone, not even my mother and sisters, because I had never heard them say anything about menstruation. No one told me that I would menstruate at a certain age. I thought menstruation was a forbidden topic, something to be ashamed of, and inappropriate to tell others. I tried to hide everything related to menstruation from others even though sometimes I experienced uncomfortable abdominal or backaches during my periods. I kept this all to myself.

We didn't have access to underwear or feminine hygiene products such as sanitary pads. Menstrual discharge flowed into our trousers during our periods. I sometimes used a piece of cloth as a menstrual pad. I wore two or three trousers together to keep the menses from seeping out if there was no fabric. We used to make the pants ourselves. My mother would cut a pants pattern and I sewed them while herding.

Instead of throwing away cloths used as pads, I buried them under the ground or in ash to prevent others from seeing blood-stained pads around my house and spreading rumors.

I felt extremely ashamed and awkward about exposing the menses on my trousers, but sometimes it was inevitable. Also, there were embarrassing moments when other women spotted the pants or accidentally stained the rug where they sat.

Locals considered girls' menstruation would occur only after their first sexual intercourse. Consequently, if girls began menstruating at an early age and locals discovered this, especially women would gossip that so-and-so family's girl must have had sex.

Unlike today, we didn't have much time to rest during our periods. I married when I was seventeen and moved into my husband's home. My daily routine was house chores, raising children, and herding livestock. The workload did not change to allow a break during my period. Sometimes I felt exhausted and suffered backaches, but there was no way to escape work. Also, we didn't pay special attention to food or drinks during our menstrual cycle, unlike girls today who avoid drinking cold water and consuming spicy food. We drank cold water and dipped our feet into rivers when herding livestock.

I didn't consult anybody when I had physical discomforts from menstruation. I thought it was shameful to let others know about my periods. Local women rarely see a doctor unless the symptoms are severe and virtually unbearable. Once, I didn't menstruate for a long time. So, I went

to the local township town for medication. I was eventually given an IV, and my menstruation resumed.

I didn't know women experienced such a thing as a menstrual cycle, and I did not know about the connection between menstruation and pregnancy until I had my first child.

Now, if I recall my menstrual experiences and compare them to the experiences of women today, our generation faced many challenges in dealing with menstruation. Our experiences were very harsh due to a lack of menstrual products and very little knowledge. Everything has changed. Women no longer encounter the challenges we had to face.

We imitated older women who considered menstruation to be shameful and dirty. Similarly, I did not tell my daughters about menstruation, nor did they ask about it. Young people and doctors are increasingly discussing menstruation publicly today and sharing relevant information and knowledge with rural women. This has helped me realize its importance and changed my conservative attitudes about menstruation.

We shouldn't be ashamed to discuss this aspect of women's experience, referring to menstruation. It is undoubtedly a part of women's health, and if we don't talk about it, many won't know how to deal with it properly. Our outdated attitudes toward menstruation have compromised women's general health and put them at risk. Women's lack of knowledge about menstruation and reluctance to talk about their physical discomforts and symptoms with families or doctors caused so many tragedies. Some women around me even died. We shouldn't feel intimidated and shy to discuss menstruation as we used to.

I now often tell my ten-year-old granddaughter about menstruation by saying, "You will menstruate. There is nothing about it that should shock you or make you feel ashamed of. It's normal for all females."

I tell her this, fearing she might conceal it as I did and feel stressed. It is beneficial to tell young girls about menstruation while they're at school to reduce their fear and anxiety when it happens. Still, I have never heard of a teacher educating young girls about menstruation at school.

There is the idea among some locals that menstruation is sinful and polluting when practicing fasting rituals or entering a religious assembly hall. Some women observe these ideas while others don't.

Menstruation is innately polluting because of its offensive odor from the unclean things removed from the uterus. It's natural for women to have a period, and women are not inferior to men because of it.

DISCUSSION

The lived experiences of these five local women have allowed us to understand better their perspectives and practices around menstruation within their traditional society. Their poignant narratives illuminate local women's challenging journeys, providing glimpses into the lives of their female forebears clothed in traditional Tibetan robes in their daily lives without feminine hygiene products.

Their transitions through menstruation, in the context of both traditional and contemporary society, distinguished their experiences from those of their female predecessors.

EVOLUTION OF CULTURAL PERCEPTIONS ON MENSTRUATION

Local women's attitudes towards menstruation have progressively changed and they now increasingly believe menstruation is not something to hide and to be ashamed of. Several factors affect local women's attitudes. First, access to modern transportation services have allowed local women to visit hospitals and contact modern medical care. Second, frequent visits to local township towns where they interact with Chinese merchants and people with different cultures. Third, the nine-year compulsory education policy compels them to send children to school where they obtain new information related to menstruation from teachers and students, which makes the topic of menstruation an open discourse. Fourth, social media allows local illiterate women to gain information about menstruation and reproductive health. All these factors gradually influence their ideas and behaviors regarding menstruation.

IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION ON REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH

All five interviewees expressed predicaments regarding menarche because of a lack of information. They all advocate educating and providing information to teenage girls about menstruation and their reproductive health so they will understand menstruation accurately and prepare for menarche. They don't want their children and grandchildren to suffer from the unnecessary psychological challenges they experienced.

ACCESS TO SANITARY PRODUCTS

All five women expressed their difficulties dealing with menstrual blood due to the lack of menstrual hygiene products. Although access to period products was limited during their menarche, these rural Tibetan women eventually had access in their later adulthood. While it is unknown when period products first became available in the local community, we do know that from the late 1990s packets of sanitary towels became available from small local stores owned by local Tibetan that also offered groceries, snacks, and beverages. These stores were also where locals gathered at night for movies and to sing traditional folk songs. Rta mgrin recalled that a bag of stacked paper towels could be folded into three to four sanitary pads and cost five *jiao*.⁹ None of the interviewees had access to sanitary pads during their menarche until the late 1990s. Mkha' 'gro skyid said:

We might have been able to get period products at the local county town or township town earlier, but we lived in an isolated area and didn't have a chance to go outside the community. For instance, I went to the local township town for the first time in my thirties when there was very limited transportation.

The five women who shared their experiences have been part of a transformative shift as trousers, sanitary pads, and undergarments became available, leading to a new era of menstrual health practices. This period saw the adoption of disposable menstrual papers other than those made from cloth-and donning multiple layered pants during menstruation. The availability of sanitary towels presented hope for women. However, effective utilization of sanitary pads was a hurdle until undergarments became available. However, even with improved accessibility, financial constraints restricted the widespread usage of menstrual pads. The financial landscape, where women's autonomy over money was limited, accentuated

⁹ Basic monetary unit of China, ten *jiao* equals one *yuan*.

this issue. Men oversaw finances, so women were compelled to make do with a frugal supply of sanitary towels, extending their usage to conserve resources. The embarrassment of purchasing sanitary products from local stores was another impediment to the rapid adoption of newer menstrual products.

STIGMA, SHAME, AND SILENCE

All five interviewees considered, at some point in their lives, that the onset of menarche was linked to sexuality. Menarche and menstruation were laden with stigma and shame, shrouding the topic in silence. Young girls were largely ignorant of menstruation until experiencing it. Menarche was inaccurately linked to being sexually active, which led to hurtful gossip, accusations, and fears for young girls. Daughters often concealed this important growth milestone from their mothers. Menarche brought confusion, guilt, distress, and internalized shame from a lack of knowledge, profoundly impacting women's mental and physical well-being while growing up.

None of the interviewees was given information or educated about menstruation by their mothers or others. Similarly, all except one interviewee were silent about their menarche. As a result, they underwent many challenging predicaments and quietly internalized the emotional turmoil menarche brought. For example, women encountered embarrassment and humiliation when working collectively in fields because of difficulty in dealing with menstrual blood and no period products. This culture of stigmatization compelled girls and women to hide everything, even severe menstrual symptoms. This was especially true for young women in the past. Shame seemed to diminish as they aged.

These negative perceptions have largely faded among younger generations due to lifestyle changes, the normalization of using sanitary products, improved medical access, and global convergence of mainstream cultures. However, exceptions exist, with certain elders reacting strongly against open discussions about menstrual health. Local women's understanding of menstrual cycles expanded as they had opportunities to interact with healthcare professionals. Yet, economic constraints made adopting health advice such as frequent and regular menstrual hygiene practices impractical. Taboos and social stigma attached to menstrual health made it more challenging to adopt constructive feedback from doctors.

CHANGING CULTURES AND MENSTRUATION

All five interviewees in this study appealed for better education for pre-menstrual girls so they would not experience serious emotional challenges when first experiencing menarche. Emotional struggles during menarche and periods and a growing understanding of menstruation have led to changes. Many local women now reject old beliefs, emphasizing the need for pre-menarche girls to be informed about menstruation before experiencing it. Furthermore, comprehensive education on menstrual and reproductive health and the promotion of the health and well-being of young girls in schools is advocated. However, implementing this in schools poses practical challenges, including a lack of leadership support, funding, educational materials, and awareness regarding the importance of teenage girls' health. Some teachers' conservative attitudes further hinder its implementation.

Contrary to the old norms, young girls now receive menstrual information from their mothers or sisters. Conversations about menstrual health are increasingly common among

young women, debunking misconceptions, and stigma. However, accurate information about menarche, menstruation, and overall reproductive health remains limited among local girls.

MENSTRUATION AND REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH

Four interviewees recounted instances where women's access to medical care and treatment was hindered by embarrassment and stigma surrounding menstruation, with three mentioning cases where women tragically lost their lives due to these barriers.

These women's experiences bear witness to the challenges faced by women in relation to menstrual health and the repercussions of a lack of accurate understanding of menstruation.

According to the interviewees, there were no historical dietary and physical labor restrictions during menstruation. However, rules have been increasingly introduced since 2000, as local women were provided with healthcare advice from medical workers regarding diet and labor practices during periods. For example, women were told to avoid spicy food, cold water, heavy physical work, and sex during the menstruation period. Drinking brown sugar tea for abdominal pain became customary. Women had increased access to healthcare providers, although they were still reserved in talking about menstrual-related issues.

Menstrual health encompasses a wide range of aspects, including physical, mental, and social well-being, and is not merely the absence of disease in relation to the menstrual cycle.¹⁰ According to UNICEF, adolescents across the globe face stigma, harassment, and social exclusion due to menstruation, leaving them particularly vulnerable. Gender inequality, discriminatory social norms, cultural taboos, and poverty can impact basic services such as toilets and sanitary products.¹¹

Menarche and menstruation have significant implications, signifying womanhood and the ability to conceive and bear children. If girls/women are not careful and not fully informed about their reproductive health, they are at risk for menstrual-related diseases, sexually transmitted diseases, and unwanted pregnancies.

PERCEPTIONS AND BELIEFS SURROUNDING MENSTRUATION

Locally, there are no specific rules on women practicing religious rituals during periods. However, more recently, some local women have come to believe that visiting sacred sites, such as the religious assembly hall and the family's shrine rooms and practicing specific religious rituals is sinful during their period because menstrual blood carries a bad smell and is considered a pollutant, though no clear explanation for why it is polluting was given. They expressed concern it might contaminate religious figures and lessen their merit.

Furthermore, there are specific practices for the disposal of used menstrual papers or cloths. Traditionally, these items were buried underground or burned in ash, as it was believed blood-stained menstrual pads should not be exposed to the sky to avoid offending spiritual beings like *klu*. Additionally, there have been instances where girls and their families have faced humiliation if menstrual pads were discovered around their homes, underscoring the importance of proper disposal practices. As a result, discussions around these issues have become less common, especially with the widespread availability of toilets equipped with garbage bins in each household.

¹⁰ See Hennegan et al. (2021).

¹¹ <https://www.unicef.org/wash/menstrual-hygiene>, accessed 20 October 2023

One interviewee highlighted a positive aspect of menstruation, citing a belief she had heard that menstrual blood, particularly during menarche, was considered precious and possessed potential medical applications.

Another interviewee mentioned the paradoxical nature of menstruation, acknowledging its discomfort while also recognizing its perceived benefits. Specifically, they mentioned that despite the distressing aspects of menstruation, it was also viewed favorably because doctors asserted that the discharge of 'unclean' substances from the uterus occurred during this process.

Furthermore, one interviewee shared a common local belief regarding the karmic implications of being born as a woman. According to this belief, women are considered to have accumulated 'less merit' and carry heavy 'karmic debts from past actions'. As a result of these karmic debts, women are believed to undergo experiences such as menstruation, pregnancy, and childbirth.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper aims to raise awareness about the significance of young women's menstrual health and underscores the urgent need to enhance education on menarche, menstruation, and reproduction for local young girls, as well as understanding menstruation accurately. This is key to fostering a healthier and more well-informed future for the next generation of young women.

Factual knowledge empowers well-informed women and young girls to know what to anticipate and how to address their biological needs. Achieving this necessitates social policy changes and support to ensure ample resources are available. Examples include providing printed and digital materials on menstrual health, offering courses on human development, supplying sanitary products at schools, increasing the presence of female doctors and healthcare workers to create a more comfortable environment for female patients, utilizing social media platforms for educational dissemination, and fostering peer-to-peer support within schools.

Educating women is educating future generations. Societies must understand that women have specific biological needs. These are not choices we are presented with at birth.

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TIBETAN TERMS

'brug skyid འབྲུག་སྐྱིད།
bon skor བོན་སྐོར།
bsod nams che བསོད་ནམས་ཚེ།
bsod nams chung བསོད་ནམས་ཚུང་།
bsod nams dman བསོད་ནམས་དམན།
bya mdo བྱ་མདོ།
dbus gtsang དབུས་གཙང་།
dpal bzang rgyal mtsho དཔལ་བཟང་རྒྱལ་མཚོ།
g.yu thog gsar ma yon tan mgon po གཡུ་ཐོག་གསར་མ་ཡོན་ཏན་མགོན་པོ།
g.yu thog rnying ma yon tan mgon po གཡུ་ཐོག་རྟིང་མ་ཡོན་ཏན་མགོན་པོ།
g.yu thog yon tan mgon po གཡུ་ཐོག་ཡོན་ཏན་མགོན་པོ།
gos rdzod གོས་རྫོད།
grang gzhi གང་གཞི།
gur kum གུར་ཀུམ།
kan su'u ཀན་སུའུ།
klu ཀུ།
lan chags ལན་ཚགས།
lha mtsho ལྷ་མཚོ།
lha sa ལྷ་ས།
lha skyid rgyal ལྷ་སྐྱིད་རྒྱལ།
mang ra མང་ར།
mkha' 'gro skyid མཁའ་འགོ་སྐྱིད།
mngal མངལ།
mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།
mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།
nag chu ནག་ཅུ།
nu ma ལུ་མ།
rta mgrin ཏ་མགྲིན།
sked pa སྐད་པ།
skye ba dman སྐེ་བ་དམན།
Tri Songdetsen, khri srong lde btsan འཇིགས་ལེ་བཙན།
zi khron ཟི་ཁྲོན།
zla mtshan ཟླ་མཚན།

CHINESE TERMS

Chengdu 成都

Gansu 甘肃

Guinan 贵南

Hainan 海南

Honghua 红花

jiao 角

Naqu 那曲

Ningxia 宁夏

Qinghai 青海

Shagou 沙沟

Sichuan 四川

Wangshenke 汪什科

Xizang 西藏

yuan 元